

Energy Analysis of a Centralized Residential Thermal System with PV-driven Heat Pumps and Multiple Storage Devices

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ABSTRACT

In the framework of the four-year EU-funded innovation project e-SAFE, a residential pilot building with ten apartments in Southern Italy will be renovated by introducing an efficient thermal system named e-THERM, with high-performance PV-assisted centralized electricity-driven heat pumps, able to satisfy both space heating/cooling needs and Domestic Hot Water (DHW) preparation. A main feature of e-THERM is the exploitation of thermal and electricity storage devices, optimized to provide high self-consumption rate

The paper describes the architecture and the control logics of e-THERM, its sizing for the pilot building in Catania and the results of a first set of dynamic simulations – carried out with a TRNSYS code – to identify the energy balances and the main efficiency figures over some typical days. The simulations are also useful to verify the potential advantage of including an electric battery to store excess PV electricity.

KEYWORDS

Heat pump, photovoltaics, thermal storage, domestic hot water, renewables, e-THERM.

INTRODUCTION

The building sector is considered as one of the largest energy consuming sectors in European Union (EU) countries, using approximately 40% of the total energy demand [1]. Around 90% of the entire EU building stock, and 78% of residential buildings only, were built before 1990, according to the EU building stock observatory [2]. The deep renovation of the existing building stock plays therefore a key role to reach the targets set by EU for 2030 and 2050, since more than 30% of the EU buildings are more than 50 years old [3].

The substantial energy demand of the existing building stock is mostly due to the poor thermal performance of their envelope components, and to the low efficiency of the heating and cooling systems. Both issues are evident in those buildings built before current EU regulations in force for addressing the energy efficiency in buildings. One of the main strategies to enhance energy efficiency in existing buildings consists in increasing the thermal performance of the envelope components, thus reducing heat losses through surfaces and thermal bridges. However, in this

context, the critical role of the domestic hot water (DHW) system is undeniable. Indeed, the energy use for DHW production currently accounts for approximately 15–40% of the total energy need in dwellings, and this proportion is likely to increase [4]: in fact, as the thermal resistance and air tightness of envelopes improve, the share of energy devoted to the space heating and cooling tends to go down, making DHW a dominant energy load in high-performance buildings. The daily trends of DHW consumptions in residential buildings exhibit random draw events clustered around specific times related to the family's daily activities. Water demand is generally higher in the morning when people wake up, when they get home from work or school in the afternoon, and before going to sleep in the evening, than at other times of the day. As reported by Fuentes et al. [5], DHW consumptions in European residential buildings vary from 80 to 160 l/day per household, with the corresponding thermal energy ranging from 4 to 9 kWh/day, depending on diverse weather conditions and cultural habits.

Available studies in the literature indicate that the energy efficiency of DHW systems is surprisingly low and that a significant amount of heat is lost from the hot water before it reaches the draw-off points [6]. Studies on the global efficiency of the DHW systems focus on the effect of storage tanks, on the use of RES in hot water generation, such as solar systems and/or Heat Pumps [7], and on strategies to control the available temperature during the day [8], also considering the Legionella issues. Hence, the DHW system may become the next bottleneck towards the low-energy buildings and sustainable development appointed by the European Commission. Therefore, novel technologies and optimisation of the entire chain of the hot water production system, in conjunction with the heating system, are required to meet the ambitious goals of the future building regulations.

In this context, the present study investigates the preliminary performance of an innovative solution for DHW production and distribution, with special emphasis on the role of control logic, hereafter called e-THERM, proposed for a pilot building, located in Catania, Italy. This study is a part of the EU-funded H2020 innovation project entitled e-SAFE (Energy and seismic affordable renovation solutions), appointing a central role to heat storage systems by developing technologies that enable effective integration and communication in heating and DHW systems.

e-THERM SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The e-THERM system, proposed in e-SAFE project, exploits the interaction of electricity-driven heat pumps and roof-mounted PV panels for on-site electricity generation. In order to make full profit of PV-based electricity production, e-THERM appoints a central role to heat storage: a first storage level is provided by large centralized water tanks, and the system is equipped with a programmable control to use the water tanks as a buffer and let the heat pump operate in the most convenient conditions (e.g. when PV electricity is available, or the outdoor air temperature exceeds a minimum threshold). The second level of thermal energy storage is provided by innovative thin and modular decentralized tanks, called hereafter e-TANK, primarily devoted to DHW storage. This system provides a higher thermal efficiency and, at the same time, a greater users' autonomy through local storages installed in each dwelling.

The distribution network can be used for the charging of e-TANK either for DHW production or for heating purposes. In both cases, the 2-pipe network can work at rather a high temperature during charging periods for few hours a day, resulting in lower heat losses from the piping network and a lower electricity consumption by the circulating pumps, compared to traditional centralised DHW systems, where the recirculating network works 24 h/day at a relatively high temperature.

The proposed e-THERM solution decouples energy production and demand while also shaving peaks in the energy demand. When applied to existing centralised DHW and H/C hydronic systems, the solution provides the replacement of existing low efficiency heat generators with EHPs driven by a PV system and the installation of new plug-play e-TANK system. The hot

water produced by EHP is delivered to each dwelling in the building – through the existing or new pipe networks – for heating service, as well as for the charging of the decentralised e-TANKs for DHW production. A hydronic module, installed within the e-TANK system, is the “intelligent” core consisting of mechanical components (valves, manifolds, pipe connectors) and control devices to manage the operation of the system according to specific control logics, while also monitoring temperatures and energy consumption for both heating and DHW.

In those buildings with a cooling service, like in the pilot building of Catania, two separate pipe networks are included, combined with two reversible EHPs: one for H/C service provided by internal fan coils, and the second one for e-TANK charging, in order to ensure a continuous and simultaneous service all year round (Figure 1). In the pilot building, both EHPs have a nominal cooling capacity of 26 kW (A35/W7). In relation to the installed heating and cooling capacities, inertial storage tanks are provided, also acting as hydraulic disconnectors (1000 L for the H/C and 1000 L for DHW line).

Figure 1. Layout of the e-THERM system for the pilot building in Catania

The e-TANK is also provided with an electric resistance (1.5 kW) that can be activated when the temperature falls below 40 °C (occasionally during the night when the system is turned off), or during anti-legionella procedure (this will be managed according to national rules). The e-TANK and the integrated hydronic module will be installed on external balconies, thus reducing impact and disturbance for the occupants during the renovation of their thermal system.

To fulfil the obligations of Italian regulations about covering a suitable RES quota – minimum 60% of the total H/C and DHW energy consumption – a photovoltaic system will be installed on the roof of the building to produce on site electricity; the PV system will be grid connected to share surplus energy or to withdraw it when PV production is not sufficient. In this pilot

project, 36 mono-crystalline photovoltaic modules will be installed, whose technical features are reported in Table 1. The total installed peak power is 13.5 kW.

Table 1. Technical features of the designed PV system

Parameter	Value
Slope	10°
Azimuth angle	9° West
Type of PV modules	Monocrystalline silicon
Efficiency in Standard Conditions (STC)	20.2%
Size of each PV module	1050 x 1770 x 35 mm
Number of PV modules	36
Overall PV surface	67 m ²
Peak Electric Power (per PV module)	375 W
Peak Electric Power (TOTAL)	13.5 kW

In order to maximise the PV exploitation, the PV system is provided with storage batteries. Their sizing has been led by the aim of charging them daily with PV electricity that is not self-consumed, while using a large share of the stored electricity to feed the heat pumps and the auxiliary devices at night or during the first hours of the day. According to these criteria and to the calculations of the hourly energy fluxes, the choice has fallen on 20 kWh capacity, divided over four storage modules (5 kWh each).

ENERGY MODEL

The energy performance of e-THERM network is investigated by means of dynamic simulations. On the one hand, the energy model to assess the space heating and cooling energy demand of the building was implemented in EnergyPlus (Figure 2), by setting the indoor temperature at 20 °C in the winter and 26 °C in the summer, considering a mean daily ventilation rate of 0.3 ACH as suggested by the Italian standard [9] and a reference activation period of the thermal systems from 1st December to 31st March for the winter, and from 1st June to 30th September for the summer. The building, in its current state, has non-insulated walls made of lightweight concrete blocks ($U = 1.1 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$); in the framework of the e-SAFE project it will be renovated through insulated timber-based panels, reaching $U = 0.32 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$. The renovation will include the thermal insulation of the roof (from $U = 1.2 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$ to $U = 0.27 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$) and the installation of high-performance windows ($U = 1.8 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$).

The reversible EHP for heating and cooling mode was modelled considering nominal data: heat capacity of 26 kW with COP of 3.2 (A7/W45) and cooling capacity of 26 kW SEER 3.5 (A35/W7). Actual performance values were calculated based on the performance curve reported by the manufacturers and taking the operating temperatures into account according to the approach suggested Italian Standard [10].

Figure 1. Current state of the pilot building in Catania, and energy model for H/C simulation

On the other hand, the simulation of the DHW system was implemented through the TRNSYS software in order to make a detailed modelling of the control logics, as well as to verify temperature trends of available DHW and energy consumption. The central storage tank has a volume of 1000 L insulated by a 75 mm polyurethane (PU) foam with heat loss coefficient of $0.4 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$, while each apartment is equipped with the decentralised hot water storage (e-TANK) with a height of 1.72 m and a volume of 140 L. Regarding e-TANK insulation, in addition to the conventional insulation by means of a PU foam, a further 8 cm layer of vacuum insulation panels (VIP) were applied to the two largest surfaces of the tank, resulted in a stand-by thermal loss equal to 0.92 kWh/day. According to the layout of the DHW network, the total length of supply and return piping is equal to 198 m. The piping network consists of tubes with different internal diameters, varying from 16.2 mm to 51.4 mm and an insulation thickness ranging from 19 mm to 33 mm, according to Italian regulation DPR 412/93. To optimize energy performance of the system, the temperature of decentralised e-TANK was set at $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ ($\pm 2.5^\circ\text{C}$), while that of the main central storage was considered as $58 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ ($\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$). An ON/OFF controller has been employed on diverter valves to regulate the charging process for the decentralised tanks, based on the setpoint temperatures, while circulating pumps works at variable volume accordingly.

Figure 3. DHW consumption profiles assumed for different apartments.

The mean daily DHW consumption for each person was considered equal to 45 Litres/day, varying slightly in each season. Furthermore, it was assumed that peaks of the daily consumption profile occur in the early morning between 06:00 and 10:00, as well as in evening between 18:00 and 22:00. Figure 3 shows the histograms of DHW consumption by ten apartments for different daily time slots in a typical winter day, with the corresponding number of residents in each dwelling, as assumed in the simulations. A specific MATLAB code was developed and linked to the TRNSYS model, using a random function (random samples from a Gaussian distribution), in order to simulate the daily DHW consumption similar to the real condition.

The technical water is supplied to the decentralised tanks by two circulating pumps – each pump for five apartments – with rated electric power of 50 W for DHW network and 100 W for H/C network. In the e-SAFE project, the energy performance of the DHW model has been evaluated under three different scenarios for the charging of the decentralised tank, corresponding to different activation periods of the circulation pump: during the entire daytime, activated twice a day, and activated three times per day. In this paper, the results for a charging strategy of e-TANK twice a day are presented (from 6:00 to 10:00 and from 18:00 to 21:00), and compared with daytime activation (from 6:00 to 22:00).

RESULTS

In this section, the main results in terms of energy consumptions are presented for both H/C and DHW, highlighting also the role of PV production.

Heating/Cooling loads

Figure 3 shows the space heating and cooling loads for the pilot building before and after renovation. The e-SAFE solutions applied to the building envelope reduce significantly heating thermal loads, while cooling loads have an important but lower reduction thanks to the shading effect of existing balconies. The positive effect of thermal insulation is twofold: on the one hand it reduces the annual energy demand, and on the other hand it allows to reduce peak loads, thus installing an EHP with lower nominal capacity.

Figure 3. Ideal heating and cooling loads, before and after e-SAFE renovation

DHW energy consumptions and losses

Figure 4 illustrates the annual electric energy consumed by the heat pump, the circulating pumps and the electric resistances in the decentralised DHW tanks, as well as the thermal energy produced by the heat pump and lost by the storage tanks and the pipe network, considering a typical control strategy for e-TANK with two charging periods per day. It can be seen that the total annual heat losses from the main storage tank and the ten decentralised e-TANKs correspond to 14.1% of the total thermal energy production, reaching a value of 32.5% if one also includes thermal losses, the latter being due to the high length of pipes and their external installation. In standard installations with internal pipe distribution, and in case of simultaneous use of pipe network for both heating and DHW charging, these losses would decrease drastically. Mean annual calculated COP value is equal to 2.87, thus slightly lower than nominal values due to higher operational set point temperature during some periods of the year. The different e-TANK charging strategies would impact on the electricity consumption of the pumps, but would only provide a small increase in the total electric energy consumption (+4% in case of continuous charging from 6:00 to 22:00, if compared with the strategy based on a twice-per day charging).

Figure 4. Annual energy balance for DHW production, storage and distribution.

However, another issue to be considered is the available DHW temperature during a day: Figure 5 shows typical temperature trends for 3 different apartments (one, three and 5 people) for the two different scenarios. It can be seen that the first scenario, with two daily charging periods, could have the risk of rather low DHW temperature when there is a request out of the operational time slots, particularly for apartments with larger number of residents (more than four people). Under these circumstances, the activation of the electrical resistance at set point temperature of 40 °C can ensure “comfort” DHW temperature, particularly at night when circulating pumps are off.

Figure 5. Temperature variations in the e-TANK and the main storage tank under different charging scenarios (two times/day and continuous from 6:00-22:00) for three different apartments (with one, three and 5 residents) in a typical winter day.

Global energy consumptions

Based on previous simulations, an evaluation of global energy consumption has been done. As shown in Figure 6, while heating and cooling are seasonal services, DHW production occurs all year round. Thanks to envelope thermal insulation, the energy consumption for H/C is quite low, showing a greater energy demand for cooling due to the specific climatic conditions of Catania. The total electricity demand for all services amount to 14375 kWh/year in case of continuous charging availability, while this would be 14129 kWh/year in the twice-a-day-charging scenario, i.e. 1% lower. Based on the previous assumptions, the share due to DHW is about 43% of the total electricity demand, which proves that – in insulated buildings – DHW production service covers a large share of the building energy demand.

Figure 6. Simulated electricity consumption for the various services during one year for the pilot building in Catania (left: hourly trends; right: annual values in kWh).

Furthermore, Figure 7 provides information about the contribution that the PV system can provide to feeding the thermal systems. The following cases are considered:

- Case 1) All the electric energy required for H/C and DHW is withdrawn from the grid;
- Case 2) With PV system (but without battery);
- Case 3) With PV system and battery.

The comparison is made for the two different scenarios of e-TANK charging, i.e. two times/day and continuous (6:00 to 22:00). On the one hand, it can be observed that, in order to maximise the use of PV electricity, the continuous charging option gives better results, because it allows

to exploit also the PV electricity available during the daytime. If no batteries are installed, the share of electric energy provided by the PV system increases from 52.2% (twice-a-day charging) to 56.7% (continuous charging). On the other hand, the importance of the battery is also evident: indeed, its installation increases the share of self-consumption respectively to 80.0% (twice-a-day charging) or 83.7% (continuous charging), thus allowing to withdraw less than 20% electricity demand from the grid.

To better understand the matching between electricity consumption and production, as well as the role of the battery, Figure 8 shows the hourly profile of electricity demand and production for two typical winter days (worst condition compared to summer days), with continuous charging option. In the winter, a simultaneous use of heating and DHW generally occurs in the first hours of the morning (6:00 to 8:00), when there is low availability of electricity from PV. Battery charge in this period is generally low and not sufficient to meet energy demand: this means that the battery is rapidly discharged, and then the electricity from external grid is used. During daytime the electricity from PV is mainly used to totally recharge the battery, and only a small quantity of PV electricity is directly consumed by the thermal system; after sunset, and especially during the charging period for the water storage tanks, electricity from the battery is largely used, thus reducing its charge below 25% of full charge.

Finally, Figure 9 shows the primary energy values (non-renewable, renewable and total). These are calculated according to official Italian Primary Energy factors for the electricity withdrawn from the net, that is to say $f_{nren} = 1.95$ for the non-renewable component and $f_{ren} = 0.47$ for the renewable component. The data also includes (renewable) thermal energy that the heat pumps take from the environment, at the evaporator. The figure suggests that the continuous charging option gives also better results in terms of renewable primary energy share: in Case 1 the total primary energy is about 66 MWh, out of which 58% is renewable and 42% non-renewable. The use of PV (Case 2) reduces the amount of electric energy withdrawn from the grid, and then the total primary energy decreases to around 55 MWh (78% coming from renewable sources). The possibility of using battery to store the PV electricity (Case 3) further reduces the total primary energy (about 49 MWh, with 91% renewable share).

Figure 7. Contribution of the PV system to the electricity demand for heating/cooling and DHW.

Figure 8. Electricity consumption and production for a typical winter day.

Figure 9. Primary energy consumption (non-renewable, renewable and total) for two different DHW charging strategies. Comparison between different PV scenarios.

CONCLUSION

This paper presents an innovative solution to reduce energy consumption for DHW production combined with hydronic heating/cooling systems. The proposed solution with two storage levels, combined with a suitable control logic, allows to optimise the matching between the global energy demand – for DHW and heating/cooling services – and the energy production from RES, in our case a PV system combined with electric batteries. The energy performance of the proposed system for the pilot building in Catania was investigated with dynamic models (hourly data output) to analyse accurately the real behaviour of the building-plant system: the results emphasize the combined effects of the technological aspects and control strategies.

One first result is that, in the retrofitted building combined with e-THERM technology, a continuous charging strategy for the storage tanks implies a slightly higher electricity consumption than a twice-per-day charging strategy (the difference is around 1%). However, the continuous charging strategy allows a better exploitation of the PV electricity, especially when the PV system is assisted by the battery: in this case, the share of electricity demand withdrawn from the national grid becomes lower than 20%. The results show that the total renewable primary energy share for heating/cooling and DHW services can reach 91% in case of continuous charging strategy, while this share decreases to 89% in case of twice-per-day charging strategy. Further increases of the renewable energy share can be achieved by increasing the PV size.

Finally, it is possible to state that, for DHW service, the thermal losses have a lower impact than in a traditional centralised system working at higher temperatures and 24 hours per day, while pipe network losses can be strongly reduced if the same pipe network is used for both heating and DHW charging.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This paper was carried out in the framework of the "Energy and seismic affordable renovation solutions" (e-SAFE) project, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 893135.

NOMENCLATURE

ACH: Air Changes per Hour
COP: Coefficient of Performance
DHW: Domestic Hot Water
EER: Energy Efficiency Ratio
EHP: Electric Heat Pump
H/C: Heating and Cooling
PV: Photovoltaic

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